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Table 2. Mean percentage of sheath rot-infected tillers 10 hills⁻¹ and yield.

Treatment ^a	% rot-infected tillers			Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	% infected panicles 10 hills ⁻¹	% nonfilled grains panicle ⁻¹
	30 DAT ^b	45 DAT	60 DAT			
1	5.2 (13.17) ^c	2.8 (9.55)	2.7 (9.44)	3.4	7.0 (14.17)	16.8 (24.21)
2	11.1 (19.47)	8.3 (6.74)	8.6 (17.06)	2.8	18.5 (25.46)	25.2 (30.12)
3	20.2 (26.69)	27.4 (31.53)	38.3 (38.22)	1.6	48.3 (44.01)	49.2 (44.55)
C.D. (5%)	2.84	3.15	5.34	0.64	4.25	6.17

^a1 = integrated method, 2 = chemical method, 3 = control. ^bDAT = days after transplanting. ^cNumbers in parentheses are arcsine VP transformations.

and applying neem cake and carbofuran just before transplanting and NSKE at 10 DAT can check the inflow of primary nematode inocula. Seed treatment, seedbed treatment with NSKP, burning of

crop residues, deep plowing and soil solarization, and neem application were prophylactic against the fungus. Results of this investigation generally agree with those of Das (1996).

Pathogenicity of cyst nematode, *Heterodera sacchari*, on rice in sand and clay soil

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The cyst nematode, *Heterodera sacchari*, occurs on rice throughout West Africa (Bridge et al 1990) but is also found outside Africa. *Oryza sativa* cultivars can be highly susceptible to *H. sacchari* (Plowright et al 1999). Production losses from *H. sacchari* infection on rice can be high under upland conditions, but are less severe under flooded conditions (Babatola 1983).

This study assessed the pathogenicity of *H. sacchari* on improved *O. sativa* cv. IDSA6 on two different soil types under upland conditions: sand (9% clay, 15% silt, 75% sand) and clay loam (20% clay, 24% silt, 56% sand). Two seeds were sown in 8-L plastic pots filled with steam-sterilized soil, and seedlings thinned to one at emergence. Pots measuring 30 cm in diameter and 25 cm deep were perforated at the base and were watered daily from the base. They were arranged on benches in a randomized complete block design. Mature cysts of *H. sacchari* were mixed into the upper 5 L of the soil

by hand, prior to sowing, at seven densities (Pi): 0, 10, 20, 50, 100, 200, and 400 cysts pot⁻¹, with 10 replications. Cysts were derived from mature IDSA6 plant roots following several generations in the pot in the screenhouse. The number of juveniles hatching into water from a subsample of cyst inoculum was assessed to estimate viable egg density.

At 84 d after sowing (DAS), plant height was measured and relative leaf chlorophyll content recorded, using the Minolta SPAD-502 meter on the uppermost fully developed leaf. At harvest, leaf dry weight was recorded after oven drying, root fresh weight was recorded after rinsing each root system and dabbing dry, and grain weight was recorded. All data were analyzed using ANOVA. The relationship between initial nematode egg density (estimated from hatching assay) and relative yield (Y) (yield obtained with no *H. sacchari* stress) was established using Yercurve for DOS software, which

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fitted the equation: $Y = Y_{min} + (1 - Y_{min})z^{(P/z)}$ where z is a constant <1 and T is the nematode population density tolerance limit [derived from Nicholson's (1933) model].

Pathogenicity of *H. sacchari* on rice was evident in sandy soil but not in clay soil (see table). Grain yield and plant growth (except in the case of leaf dry weight, LDW) decreased at higher *H. sacchari* densities in sand but not in clay. Relative minimum yield in sandy soil was lower (0.15) than that observed in clay soil (0.6) over the range of *H. sacchari* Pi in the study (see figure). Relationships between Y and egg Pi (P) were described as

$$\text{Sand: } Y = 0.464 + 2.628 \times 0.15^{(P-0)} \quad R^2 = 0.22$$

$$\text{Clay: } Y = 3.552 + 2.368 \times 0.05^{(P-0.93)} \quad R^2 = 0.11$$

In both soil types, the term z was low, representing a high damage potential of individual nematodes of the first generation. In sand, no tolerance limit was

detected; in clay, it was calculated as 0.93 eggs mL⁻¹ soil. No differences in plant height between treatments in clay soil were observed at 84 DAS, although differences were observed at earlier growth stages. The root systems of infected plants were blackened, necrotic, and appeared stubby. This impairs the function of roots, particularly under conditions of low water availability.

H. sacchari is clearly highly pathogenic on susceptible upland rice in sandy soil. Very low initial population densities resulted in severe grain losses in sandy soil, whereas, in the heavier clay soil, rice was more tolerant of *H. sacchari*. The chlorosis, reduced vigor, and root damage observed in *H. sacchari*-infected plants are likely to further predispose crops to

existing stresses, such as weed competition and drought, exacerbating overall losses. *H. sacchari* egg Pi fitted the critical point model well, despite the presence of multiple nematode generations over the duration of the crop cycle. The good fit of *H. sacchari* to the model is attributed to the aggressiveness of the parasite early in the plant's growth. Field population densities similar to those used in the study likely occur in the field (Coyne et al 1996); moreover, conditions are representative of seedbed conditions. *H. sacchari* is therefore a potentially important threat to the sustainability of intensive upland rice production in West Africa, particularly with improved cultivars on sandy soils.

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Effect of *Heterodera sacchari* Pi cyst density on development of rice cv IDSA6 in sand and clay loam soil.*

Cyst density (L soil)	Sandy soil					Clay soil				
	GY	RFW	LDW	HT	RLCC	GY	RFW	LDW	HT	RLCC
0	3.5	19.1	7.5	904	33.2	6.4	9.4	9.7	960	28.8
1.25	1.6	12.3	10.3	889	31.1	6.9	10.7	10.9	985	28.6
2.5	2.8	9.7	7.3	918	30.8	6.5	8.5	8.1	879	28.1
6.25	1.7	8.2	6.3	667	22.2	4.9	9.2	8.7	947	28.4
12.5	1.8	5.8	7.8	707	31.6	5.2	9.0	8.7	916	30.3
25	1.2	5.2	5.8	642	33.1	5.3	8.7	7.4	899	28.5
50	0.9	2.9	5.2	429	15.0	3.5	5.5	5.1	754	26.1
LSD										
<0.05	1.63	6.8	ns	257	10.1	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
<0.01	ns	9.0	-	342	13.4	-	-	-	-	-
Interaction ^b	***	ns	ns	***	ns					

*GY = grain yield (g), RFW = root fresh weight (g), LDW = leaf dry weight (g), HT = plant height (mm) at 84 DAS, RLCC = relative leaf chlorophyll content at 84 DAS. LSD = least significant difference. ^bInteraction *H. sacchari* inoculum density × soil type. ***Significantly different at P<0.001, ns = not significant at P<0.05.

Relative yield (g)

Relationship between relative yield of rice cv. IDSA6 and *Heterodera sacchari* Pi egg density in sandy and clay loam soils.

A simple method for evaluating the virulence of the brown planthopper

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To effectively use rice varieties resistant to the brown planthopper [BPH, *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål)], it is necessary to monitor the virulence of BPH populations. BPH virulence is controlled

polygenically. This character, however, does not exhibit a continuous distribution of phenotype but is a threshold character that has two distinct phenotypes—virulent and avirulent (Tanaka 1999).

Hence, a proportion of virulent individuals in a BPH population indicates a degree of virulence. For virulence tests of BPH individuals, many researchers have measured honeydew excretion of BPH